

RELEASE

Handbook
Good Practices
&
Practical Alternatives

Executive Summary

Funded by the European Union

This Handbook builds upon the data collected throughout the RELEASE project, in particular, the practitioners-participants' experiences voiced in the events organized within the project. Different backgrounds represented by the target groups (judges, prosecutors and lawyers) helped to collect and compile a cross-professional panorama of good practices and gaps. Therefore, the Handbook is based on different points of view that will help for a better understanding of how alternative measures can be applied at the national level and to facilitate mutual understanding and cooperation among different professionals - with a common goal of imposing pre-trial detention as a measure of last resort.

The RELEASE project revealed the difficulties in the application of the ECtHR standards relating to alternative measures. Therefore, the first section summarizes the key points stemming from the relevant Court's case-law. In addition, the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/681 is outlined to help navigate with the EU standards.

Section two includes best practices identified through cross-professional activities. The key points for each profession are the following:

1) Lawyers:

- first actions with the suspect are often crucial in determining preventive measures. They help in gathering information, which may lead to the application of alternative measures instead of pre-trial detention,
- lawyers may help to decide on alternative measures by presenting the particular situation of the suspect,
- questing the sole reasoning behind the decision on preventive measures can help embrace ECtHR standards and develop the practice of making properly reasoned and justified decisions when imposing these measures.

2) Judges

- an individual evaluation of the suspect's position when applying preventive measures is crucial,
- fair and elaborated reasoning of the judicial decision, which is embedded in individual circumstances of the case, is needed in every case,
- judges should always consider applying a combination of measures, or application of a shorter period of pre-trial detention. Incorporation of ECHR case law into national case law in this regard is recommended,

3) Prosecutors:

- individual evaluation of the suspect reflected in duly reasoned and justified decisions on preventive measures is needed in every case,
- collaboration with probation officers and the use of rehabilitation programmes may prove efficient in specific circumstances, for example, if suspects suffer from addictions or mental issues,
- in EU cross-border cases, the European Supervision Order may be used as an alternative which enables the cross-border supervision of non-custodial preventive measures.

The last section outlines the European Supervision Order, the EU cooperation instrument which enables the supervision of non-custodial preventive measures by another Member State in which a suspect resides whilst awaiting trial.